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Generalized Trust in the Italian Regions

It grew by an average of 10.54% between 2010 and 2022

Istat calculates the value of generalized trust. Generalized trust is defined as the percentage of people aged 14 and over who believe that most people are trustworthy out of the total number of people aged 14 and over.

Ranking of the regions by value of generalized trust in 2022. Trentino Alto Adige is in first place by value of generalized trust in 2022 with an amount equal to 41.7 units, followed by Lazio with a value equal to 30.6 units, and from Valle d'Aosta with an amount of 30 units. In the middle of the table are Piedmont with an amount of 25.7 units, followed by Emilia Romagna with a value of 25.2 units, and Tuscany with an amount of 24.8. Molise closes the ranking with a value of 17.8 units, followed by Campania with a value of 17.5 units and Sicily with a value of 16.2 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in generalized trust between 2010 and 2022. Calabria is in first place by value of the percentage change in generalized trust between 2010 and 2022 with an amount of 36.77% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 15.5 units up to an amount of 21.2 units. Lazio follows with a variation from an amount of 30.77% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 23.4 units up to a value of 30.6 units or equal to an amount of 7.2 units. In third place is Basilicata with a variation of 24.53% corresponding to an amount from 15.9 units up to a value of 19.8 units. In the middle of the table are Emilia Romagna with an amount of 12.5% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 22.4 units up to a value of 25.2 units equal to 2.8 units. Trentino Alto Adige follows with a variation equal to 10.32% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 37.8 units up to a value of 41.7 units equal to 3.9 units. In eleventh place are Lombardy with an amount equal to 8.5% corresponding to a variation from 24.7 units up to a value of 26.8 units. Liguria and Sardinia close the ranking with a variation of 0.00%, followed by Molise with a value of -10.55%. On average, the value of generalized trust in the Italian regions grew from an amount equal to 22.1 units up to a value of 24.5 units or corresponding to a growth of 10.54% equal to 2.3 units.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we identify a clustering with a k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Two clusters are therefore identified:

- Cluster 1: Valle d'Aosta, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Liguria, Lombardy, Lazio, Trentino Alto Adige, Emilia Romagna, Piedmont, Tuscany, Veneto;
- Cluster 2: Molise, Puglia, Calabria, Sicily, Campania, Basilicata, Abruzzo, Umbria, Marche, Sardinia.

From the point of view of the average value of the clusters it is possible to identify the following ordering i.e. Cluster 1 > Cluster 2. We can note that Cluster 1 is essentially made up of regions in the Centre-North. On the contrary, the southern regions tend to be present in Cluster 2 with the exception of Abruzzo and Umbria. It follows that the regions of the Centre-North, which have high per capita

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incomes, also have a higher level of generalized trust than the southern regions. It is likely that the high values of generalized trust in the Central-Northern regions are both an effect and a cause of the higher per capita income compared to the southern regions.

Generalized trust in the Italian macro-regions between 2010 and 2022. The Central Italy is the first Italian macro-region in terms of percentage growth in generalized trust equal to an amount of 18.53%. However, generalized trust also grew in the other Italian macro-regions such as in the South with +14.62%, North-East with +14.62%, Southern Italy with +12.35%, North with +9.39 %, North-West with +7.72%, Islands +1.78%. However, there is a significant gap between the regions of Central-Northern Italy and the regions of Southern Italy. In fact, the value of generalized trust in Southern Italy is 28.72% lower than in Central Italy, -28.20% compared to the North-East, -26.86% compared to the North, -26.03% in the North-West .

Conclusions. The value of generalized trust grew between 2010 and 2022 by an amount equal to 10.54%. The growth occurred in all Italian regions with the exception of Liguria and Sardinia which had a variation of 0.00% and Molise, the only region in which the value of generalized trust decreased by 10.55%. The northern regions show that they have a much higher value of generalized trust than the value of the southern regions. The southern regions also suffer from a generalized lack of trust compared to the northern regions. It is likely that generalized trust has a dual effect in the sense of economic growth, that is, on the one hand, trust enables economic growth, offering support to investors and entrepreneurs, and on the other hand, trust is an output of economic growth, since positive results obtained can create further enthusiasm and therefore induce further investments. On the contrary, low trust can lead to under-investment, under-employment and can lead to a system oriented towards under-productivity. In fact, there is no doubt that trust in others increases the orientation towards productivity, especially in private initiatives, offering greater resources and goods both to the real economy and to the growth of social capital.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Macro-Regioni	2010	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Nord	24,5	26,8	2,30	9,39
Nord-ovest	24,6	26,5	1,90	7,72
Nord-est	24,3	27,3	3,00	12,35
Centro	23,2	27,5	4,30	18,53
Mezzogiorno	17	18,8	1,80	10,59
Sud	17,1	19,6	2,50	14,62
Isole	16,9	17,2	0,30	1,78
Italia	21,7	24,3	2,60	11,98

Regione	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Piemonte	23,7	21	21,3	22,3	26,3	20,8	20,2	22	21,3	26,9	23,7	27,5	25,7
Valle d'Aosta	25,8	32,6	28,2	33	28,2	26,1	27,5	26	31,1	30,2	29,4	33,3	30
Liguria	26,3	28,3	27,7	25,4	25,3	22,5	25,7	23,1	21,5	28,4	24,8	25,2	26,3
Lombardia	24,7	22,8	22,6	22,1	24	21,9	21,2	22,3	23,8	27,2	25,2	28	26,8
Trentino-Alto Adige	37,8	35,3	30,7	32,8	33,8	31,3	29,5	36,8	37,1	37,8	38	38,4	41,7
Veneto	22,6	23,6	20,3	22,2	22	19,5	21,6	18,6	24,2	25,8	25,4	26,4	25,9
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	26,6	29,3	23,5	21,4	25,4	22,8	23,6	25,8	24,8	24,9	28	29,2	27,5
Emilia-Romagna	22,4	20,7	22,8	22,6	27,5	22	20,6	21	22,7	23,7	24,8	27,9	25,2
Toscana	23,6	21,5	20,4	20,5	25,9	24,1	20,3	20,4	24,7	25,7	24,5	26,2	24,8
Umbria	21,8	22,8	17,6	23,4	18,6	18,7	18,2	17,8	20,5	22,6	18,9	22,6	26
Marche	22,2	20	16,6	20,3	18,4	24,1	18,5	17,8	22,2	22,2	22	24,2	22,8
Lazio	23,4	22,8	25	24,9	28,6	22,5	22	23,1	20,1	24,1	24,6	28,3	30,6
Abruzzo	20	19,3	19,5	18,1	22,2	18,8	17,1	16,8	18,1	23	24,4	25,6	22,7
Molise	19,9	19,4	14	17,3	18,3	15,5	15,6	16,5	15,8	17,2	19,2	20,8	17,8
Campania	15,2	17,2	14,4	17,1	20,8	17,1	20,1	19,7	19,6	23,1	20,5	24,5	17,5
Puglia	19,5	16,1	14,3	15,5	18,2	14	15,1	14,2	17,4	20,6	21,6	20,1	20,9
Basilicata	15,9	14,7	13,8	18,2	22,8	17,9	23,3	19,1	14,5	19,4	20	23,8	19,8
Calabria	15,5	18,7	20,4	19	17,8	17,1	15,5	12,7	16,2	18,4	23,4	23,7	21,2
Sicilia	15,8	14,7	12,3	15,3	17,4	12,7	12,5	11,8	13,3	16,1	13,7	16,1	16,2
Sardegna	20,2	25,4	20,1	23,5	21,8	19,9	18	19,4	17	20,1	23	24,7	20,2

